

ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE ATTRIBUTES

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Abstract

This study examined the academic performance attributes of the selected grade six pupils of the identified public elementary schools of SDO-Bayawan City. It employed descriptive method. A questionnaire was used to generate data that measured the variables. It was administered to the respondents and the answers generated were tabulated and analyzed. Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the academic performance of the grade six pupils was at satisfactory level. It is recommended that the proposed programs, activities, and projects can be adopted by the public elementary schools of Bayawan City Division.

Keywords: *academic performance attributes, descriptive method*

I. INTRODUCTION

The success of educational institutions is measured by the academic performance attributes of its students. As career competition grows even fiercer in the working world, the importance of students doing well in school has caught the attention of parents, legislators, and government education departments. In line with this, Malik et al. (2016) put forward how students' academic achievement serves as mechanism for societal development and economic improvements.

Furthermore, students are most the essential asset for any educational institute. The social and economic development of the country is directly linked with students' performance. Moreover, academic achievement plays an important role in producing best quality graduates who will in turn become leaders and manpower of the country (Maganga, 2016).

Hence, as academic performance is an apparent phenomenon in developing countries like the Philippines whereby success of academic programs is measured how well learners meet the set standards, this research aims to examine the academic performance of the selected grade six pupils of the identified public elementary schools of SDO-Bayawan serving as basis for the formulation of programs, activities, and projects in different learning areas.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design. The study utilized a descriptive method to show the results of the academic performance attitudes of the selected Grade VI pupils of DepEd – Bayawan City Division.

Research Environment. The locale of the study was DepEd's Bayawan City Division's Public Elementary Schools.

Research Respondents. The research respondents were the 300 pupils of the selected public elementary schools of DepEd - Bayawan City Division.

Research Instruments. The study utilized an adapted questionnaire from Chapman to collect the needed data for the undertaking.

Research Procedure. The questionnaires were distributed to the respondents after the necessary permissions acquired from the respective school heads. Interviews were conducted to obtain data which may not be clearly indicated by the respondents in the questionnaire. Records reviews was done focusing on the responses of the pupils, teachers, and school heads regarding the academic performance of the pupils. The data were finally analyzed.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1. *Academic Performance in English*

English	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Outstanding	78	26.00
Very Satisfactory	73	24.30
Satisfactory	149	49.70
Total	300	100.00

Table 1 presents the academic performance of the grade six pupils in English using the following categories like outstanding, very satisfactory, and satisfactory. Based on the data given, 78 of the pupils or 20 percent satisfactory ratings and 149 or 49.70 percent were in satisfactory level.

It could be inferred that majority of the pupils obtained satisfactory ratings in English as compared to the percentage for very satisfactory and outstanding. This is affirmed the study of Sumagaysay (2017) revealing academic performance rating of English students especially in their reading skills and competence.

Hence, pupil's academic performance in English needs to be advanced from satisfactory to outstanding, projects such as READ: Reading Advocacies of the Division could be adopted.

Table 2. *Academic Performance in Mathematics*

Mathematics	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Outstanding	83	27.70
Very Satisfactory	71	23.60
Satisfactory	146	48.70
Total	300	100.00

Table 2 shows the academic performance of grade six pupils and it manifested their level of learning in Mathematics. There were 83 or 27.70 percent of the respondents who garnered an outstanding rating, 71 or 23.60 percent got very satisfactory and 146 or 48.70 were in satisfactory levels. The survey showed the need to advance academic performance in Mathematics from satisfactory to outstanding. This is supported by the findings shared by Toong (2015) on the use of different teaching strategies to nurture pupils’ mathematical skills and analytical thinking. Furthermore, Project LINE: Literacy Improvements and numeracy Engagements could be adopted by teachers handling Mathematics .

Table 3. *Academic Performance in Science*

Science	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Outstanding	83	27.70
Very Satisfactory	66	22
Satisfactory	151	50.30
Total	300	100.00

Total 3 indicates the academic performance of the grade six pupils in Science wherein 83 or 27.70, 66 or 22.00 percent, and 151 or 50.30 percent obtained outstanding, very satisfactory ratings respectively. The results showed that only few of the pupils got outstanding rating in Science subject. In fact, Sinco (2018) in her study put forward the use of strategic intervention materials to improve students’ academic performance in Science.

Table 4. *Academic Performance in Filipino*

Filipino	Frequency (f)	Percentage
Outstanding	73	24.30
Very Satisfactory	88	29.40
Satisfactory	139	46.30
Total	300	100.00

As shown in Table 4, the academic performance of grade six pupils in Filipino resorted into 73 or 24.30 percent , 88 or 29.40 percent and 139 or 46.30 percent for outstanding , very satisfactory , and satisfactory levels respectively . The data further showed that majority of the respondents got satisfactory ratings. In line with this, Epon (2019) shared in his study the different factors affecting performance of pupils in Filipino most especially the use of differentiated instruction.

Table 5. *Academic Performance in Araling Panlipunan*

Araling Panlipunan	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Outstanding	88	29.30
Very Satisfactory	77	25.70
Satisfactory	125	45.00
Total	300	100.00

Table 5 describes the Grade Six pupils academic performance in Araling Panlipunan where 88 or 29.30 percent, 77 or 25.70 percent, and 125 or 45.00 percent got outstanding, very satisfactory, and satisfactory ratings respectively. It means that majority of the respondents manifest satisfactory ratings.

IV. CONCLUSION

The academic performance of the grade Vi pupils was at satisfactory level in different learning areas of English, Mathematics, Science, Filipino, and Araling Panlipunan.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. To improve the pupils' academic performance in the different learning areas, a number of programs, activities and projects (PAPs) could be undertaken by the Public Elementary School Teachers like Project READ: Reading Enhancement Advocacies of the Division for English, Project LINE: Literacy Improvement and Numeracy Enhancement for Mathematics, Project RED – SIMS: Reading with Efficiency and Deep Understanding Utilizing Strategic and Interactive Materials for Least Learned Competencies in Science, Project N3: Napili. Nagsanay. Nakabasa for Filipino, and Project SIKAP: Samu't-saring Impormasyon, Kaisipan, at Kaalaman sa Araling Panlipunan.
2. Public elementary school teachers should be given training activities in answer to their professional development needs on pedagogical retooling. Project SEARCH: Skills' Enhancement and Advancement through Rearing, Coaching, and Helping Teachers could be implemented.

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